

Mononuclear iron complexes derived from tridentate ligands : Synthesis, characterization, DFT calculations and DNA interaction studies[†]

Sweety Rathi, Ankur Maji, Ovender Singh and Kaushik Ghosh*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, Roorkee-247 667, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : ghoshfcy@iitr.ernet.in Fax : 91-1332-273560

Abstract : Mononuclear iron(II)/(III) complexes derived from tridentate 3N donor ligands 1-phenyl-1-(pyridine-2-ylmethyl)-2-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)hydrazine (H-N₃L) and 1-phenyl-2-(1-(pyridin-2-yl)ethylidene)-1-(pyridin-2-ylmethyl)hydrazine (Me-N₃L) have been synthesized. Complexes Fe(H-N₃L)Cl₃ (1), [Fe(H-N₃L)₂](ClO₄)₂ (2), Fe(Me-N₃L)Cl₃ (3) and [Fe(Me-N₃L)₂](ClO₄)₂ (4) have been characterized using various spectroscopic techniques. Theoretical studies were also performed for the representative complex Fe(H-N₃L)Cl₃ (1) to evaluate the structural parameters. Electrochemical studies were investigated for the representative complexes. DNA interaction studies were investigated using UV-visible absorption spectral studies, ethidium bromide displacement assay and circular dichroism spectral studies. Nuclease activity was investigated by DNA gel electrophoresis.

Keywords : Iron complexes, theoretical studies, electrochemistry, DNA binding, nuclease activity.

Introduction

Mononuclear iron complexes having tridentate 3N donor are of extreme current interest in several areas of chemical research. For the structural and functional modelling of metal sites mononuclear iron enzymes such as catechol dioxygenase (CDO)¹, superoxide dismutase (SOD)². Several groups are interested in designing oxidation catalyst with such kind of mononuclear iron complexes. In this regard, Que and co-workers have utilized a tetradentate ligand TPA for the synthesis of iron complexes. These complexes were utilized for the functional modelling of non heme iron enzymes capable of alkane functionalization³. Hitomi and co-workers have reported iron complexes derived from ligands having nitrogen donors. These complexes were found to be potent applicant in the hydroxylation of alkane C-H bonds with high selectivity⁴. Roelfes *et al.* have synthesized iron complexes using N4Py a pentadentate ligand. This complex was proved to be an efficient catalyst for diverse substrate oxidation reactions⁵. Iron complexes derived from nitrogen donor ligands have been shown remarkable magnetic properties as in spin state crossover⁶ and also used as polymerization catalyst⁷. We have been working with ligand Pyimpy, Me-Pyimpy and recently reported spontaneous reduction and nuclease activity of iron complexes⁸.

Such types of ligands are similar to bis iminopyridine ligands reported by Chirik and co-workers which have shown several type of interesting activities⁹.

As a part of our ongoing research¹⁰ we have designed ligand H-N₃L and Me-N₃L and synthesized mononuclear iron complexes Fe(H-N₃L)Cl₃ (1), [Fe(H-N₃L)₂](ClO₄)₂ (2), Fe(Me-N₃L)Cl₃ (3) and [Fe(Me-N₃L)₂](ClO₄)₂ (4). These complexes were characterized spectroscopically using IR, UV-visible, NMR and ESI-MS spectroscopy. Theoretical calculations were also elucidated the geometrical and structural parameters. TD-DFT was also monitored for the representative complex 1 to study the electronic properties. Electrochemical studies were also performed for complexes 1 and 2. These complexes were found to be stable in aqueous buffer system and hence subjected to DNA binding and nuclease studies. Complex 1 exhibited effective oxidative cleavage in presence of H₂O₂.

Experimental

Materials :

Anhydrous FeCl₃ was purchased from Rankem, New Delhi, India, Fe(ClO₄)₂.xH₂O, 2-chloromethylpyridine hydrochloride from Sigma Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany. Analytical grade reagents hydrogen peroxide was pur-

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

chased from S. D. Fine, Mumbai, India, methyl-2-pyridyl ketone from Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. Supercoiled *pBR322* DNA and CT DNA were purchased from Bangalore Genei (India). Ethidium bromide (EB) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Germany). Tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane-HCl (Tris-HCl) buffer and phosphate buffer were prepared in deionised water. All the chemicals are of reagent grade and used as purchased. Solvents used for spectroscopic studies were HPLC grade and purified by standard procedures before use.

Methods and instrumentation :

Elemental analysis was carried out on Elemental model Vario EL-III. Infrared spectra were recorded (range 4000–400 cm^{-1}) as KBr pellets on a Nicolet NEXUS Aligent 1100 FT-IR spectrometer, using 50 scans and were reported in cm^{-1} . Electronic spectra were recorded in methanol and phosphate buffer solution with UV-2450, Shimadzu, UV-Visible spectrophotometer using cuvettes of 1 cm path length. Fluorescence spectra were recorded by RF5301PC Shimadzu spectrofluorophotometer. Circular dichroism (CD) spectra were recorded on Chirascan circular dichroism spectrometer, Applied photophysics, UK. Molar conductivities were determined in DMF at 10^{-3} M at 25 °C with a Systronics conductometer. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AVANCE, 500.13 MHz, Jeol delta NMR spectrometer, chemical shifts for ^1H NMR spectra are related to internal standard Me_4Si for all residual protium in the deuterated solvents. The electrospray ionisation (ESI) mass spectra of the complexes were recorded as acetonitrile solutions in positive ion mode with a Bruker MicroTOF-QII mass spectrometer. Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were determined at 300 K with Cryogenic Ltd. vibrating sample magnetometer. In order to investigate the redox behavior of the synthesized complexes, electrochemical studies were performed on a CHI-600 electroanalyser in dichloromethane and acetonitrile with 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as supporting electrolyte. The working electrode, reference electrode and auxiliary electrode were glassy carbon, Ag/AgCl and Pt wire electrode respectively. The concentration of the compounds was in the order of 10^{-3} M. The ferrocene/ferrocenium couple occurs at $E_{1/2} = +0.49$ V vs Ag/AgCl under the same experimental conditions.

Synthesis of ligands :

Tridentate ligands $\text{H-N}_3\text{L}$ and $\text{Me-N}_3\text{L}$ have been synthesized and described elsewhere¹¹.

Fig. 1. Tridentate ligands $\text{H-N}_3\text{L}$ and $\text{Me-N}_3\text{L}$.

Synthesis of iron complexes :

Caution! Perchlorate salts of metal complexes with organic ligands are potentially explosive. Only small amount of material should be prepared and handled with caution.

$\text{Fe}(\text{H-N}_3\text{L})\text{Cl}_3$ (1) : To a solution of $\text{H-N}_3\text{L}$ (0.5 mmol, 0.144 g) in methanol : ethanol (1 : 1) was added similar equivalent of $\text{NEt}_4[\text{FeCl}_4]$ (0.5 mmol, 0.163 g) in 2 mL methanol : ethanol (1 : 1) dropwise. Stirring of reaction mixture was continued for 3 h and then it was filtered. Evaporation of solvent afforded red-brown colored precipitate. Yield : 70%. UV-Visible [CH_3OH , $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)]: 452 (500), 343 (7520), 300 (4930), 259 (7960), 221 (10740). Selected IR data (KBr, $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 1606, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}_{\text{imine}}}$. μ_{eff} (303 K) : 5.91 B.M. $\Lambda_{\text{M}}/\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ (in DMF) : 52. ESI-MS (m/z) : 414.1428 $[\text{M}-\text{Cl}]^+$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_3\text{Fe}$: C, 52.08; H, 3.89; N, 13.50. Found : C, 49.97; H, 4.05; N, 13.32.

$[\text{Fe}(\text{H-N}_3\text{L})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (2) : Ligand $\text{H-N}_3\text{L}$ (0.5 mmol, 0.144 g) was taken in 10 mL of methanol and stirred. To this stirred solution $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.25 mmol, 0.063 g) in 2–3 mL of methanol was added dropwise. Color changes to red and reaction was stirred further for 3–4 h. Reaction was filtered and left for solvent evaporation. The solid obtained after evaporation was washed with small amount of methanol and diethylether. Complex was recrystallized in dichloromethane : methanol mixture. Yield : 68%. UV-Visible [CH_3OH , $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)]: 340 (31290), 294 (11010), 258 (14840), 238 (24155). Selected IR data (KBr, $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 1606, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$, 1091, 623, $\nu_{\text{ClO}_4^-}$. μ_{eff} (303 K) : 0.51 B.M. $\Lambda_{\text{M}}/\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ (in DMF) : 156. ESI-MS (m/z) : 731.1615 $[\text{M}-\text{ClO}_4]^+$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_8\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_8\text{Fe}$: C, 52.00; H, 3.88; N, 13.48. Found : C, 51.77; H, 3.22; N, 13.02.

$\text{Fe}(\text{Me-N}_3\text{L})\text{Cl}_3$ (3) : To a solution of $\text{Me-N}_3\text{L}$ (0.5 mmol, 0.151 g) in methanol : ethanol (1 : 1) was added similar equivalent of $\text{NEt}_4[\text{FeCl}_4]$ (0.5 mmol, 0.163 g) in

2 mL methanol : ethanol (1 : 1) dropwise. Reaction mixture was continued to stir for 3 h and filtered. Evaporation of solvent afforded red-brown colored precipitate. Yield : 64%. UV-Visible [CH_3OH , $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 435 (790), 329 (3980), 260 (6500), 225 (8220). Selected IR data (KBr, $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 1595, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{Nimine}} \cdot \mu_{\text{eff}}$ (303 K) : 5.40 B.M. $\Lambda_{\text{M}}/\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ (in DMF) : 41. ESI-MS (m/z) : 428.0220 $[\text{M}-\text{Cl}]^+$, 325.1410 $[\text{L}+\text{Na}]^+$, 301.1438 $[\text{L}+\text{H}]^+$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_3\text{Fe}$: C, 53.18; H, 4.23; N, 13.06. Found : C, 51.85; H, 4.42; N, 12.83.

$[\text{Fe}(\text{Me}-\text{N}_3\text{L})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**4**) : To the stirred solution of ligand $\text{Me}-\text{N}_3\text{L}$ (0.5 mmol, 0.151 g) in 10 mL of methanol was added a methanolic solution $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.25 mmol, 0.063 g) was added dropwise. A dark red color precipitate appeared. The reaction mixture was stirred further for 4 h. Reaction was filtered and solvent was removed. The solid obtained after evaporation was washed with small amount of methanol and diethylether. Complex was recrystallized for further analysis. Yield : 63%. UV-Visible [CH_3OH , $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 552 (350), 345 (8720), 285 (9790), 250 (27740). Selected IR data (KBr, $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 1597, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$, 1091, 623, $\nu_{\text{ClO}_4^-} \cdot \mu_{\text{eff}}$ (303 K) : 2.25 B.M. $\Lambda_{\text{M}}/\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ (in DMF) : 148. ESI-MS (m/z) : 759.1790 $[\text{M}-\text{ClO}_4]$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_8\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_8\text{Fe}$: C, 53.10; H, 4.22; N, 13.04. Found : C, 52.88; H, 4.19; N, 12.92.

Theoretical studies :

DFT calculations were performed on Fe^{III} complex at the B3LYP level using LANL2DZ basis set for iron center and 6-31G(d) basis set for non metal atoms¹². Time dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) was also utilized to obtain electronic transitions with their transition probability.

DNA interaction studies :

DNA interactions with small molecules were investigated by absorption titration, fluorescence quenching and circular dichroism spectral studies. DNA interaction studies were performed in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) and stocks were prepared in dimethylformamide for better solubility of complexes in the aqueous buffer system. Stability of the complexes was examined in phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) for 6 h. DNA binding experiments were monitored in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) using a

solution of calf thymus DNA (CT-DNA) which showed the ratio of UV-Visible absorbance at 260 and 280 nm (A_{260}/A_{280}) of *ca.* 1.8, indicating that the CT-DNA was sufficiently protein free¹³. The concentration of DNA solution was calculated using absorbance at 260 nm and the extinction coefficient ϵ_{260} was taken as $6600\text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ as reported in the literature¹⁴. Absorbance titration experiments were carried out using a fixed concentration of complex with varying concentration of CT-DNA in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2). Binding constants (K_b) were evaluated from a plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ using the equation¹⁵ :

$$[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f) = [\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f) + 1/[K_b(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_b)]$$

where $[\text{DNA}]$ is the concentration of DNA in base pairs. The apparent absorption coefficients ϵ_a , ϵ_f and ϵ_b represent $A_{\text{obs}}/[\text{Complex}]$, the extinction coefficient of free complexes and the extinction coefficient of complexes in fully bound form, respectively. The binding mode of metal complexes with CT-DNA can be predicted by observing the changes in the absorption spectra as well as the strength of binding constant (K_b).

Ethidium bromide (EB) displacement experiments using fluorescence spectroscopy were also monitored for better understanding of mode of DNA interaction with the complexes. EB emits intense fluorescence in presence of DNA due to its strong intercalation between adjacent DNA-base pairs. Addition of complexes to the EB-DNA mixture may lead to the quenching of enhanced fluorescence of EB suggesting a competitive binding towards DNA. Fluorescence quenching experiments were carried out by successive addition of a fixed amount of complexes to the DNA solutions pretreated with 5–10 μM EB in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2). These samples were excited at 250 nm and emissions were observed between 500 and 700 nm. Stern-Volmer quenching constants were calculated using the given equation.

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{\text{SV}} Q,$$

where I_0 and I are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of complex and Q is the concentration of quencher (complexes **1-4**). K_{SV} is a linear Stern-Volmer constant and given by the ratio of slope to intercept in the plot of I_0/I versus Q ¹⁶.

The CD spectrum of CT-DNA in the range 225–300 nm shows one positive band at 278 nm due to base stack-

ing and one negative band at 246 nm due to helicity¹⁷. Circular dichroism (CD) spectra of CT-DNA in absence and presence of the iron complexes were recorded with a 0.1 cm path-length cuvette after 10 min incubation at 25 °C. The concentration of the complexes and CT-DNA were 50 and 200 mM respectively. The mode of interaction of metal complexes with DNA can be evaluated on the basis of change in molar ellipticity values and shifting in the position of positive and negative bands.

Nuclease studies :

Cleavage of plasmid *pBR322* DNA was monitored using agarose gel electrophoresis. Supercoiled *pBR322* DNA (100 ng) in TBE (pH 8.2) was treated with complex **1** dissolved in dimethylformamide (10%) in the presence or absence of additives (24 μL in total volume). The oxidative DNA cleavage by the complex **1** was studied in the presence of H₂O₂ (oxidizing agent). The samples were incubated for 2 h at 37 °C and after incubation loading buffer (25%) bromophenol blue and 30% glycerol was added. The agarose gel (0.8%) containing 0.4 μg/mL of EB was prepared and the electrophoresis of the DNA cleavage products was performed on it. The gel was run at 60 V for 2 h in TBE buffer and the bands were identified by placing the stained gel under an illuminated UV lamp. The fragments were photographed by using gel documentation system (BIO RAD).

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

Tridentate ligands have been synthesized using Schiff's base condensation of amine 1-phenyl-1-(pyridine-2-

ylmethyl)hydrazine with the corresponding aldehyde in methanol. The aldehyde used for the synthesis of ligand H-N₃L and Me-N₃L are 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde and 2-acetylpyridine respectively.

Mononuclear iron complex Fe(H-N₃L)Cl₃, **1** was synthesized using Et₄N[FeCl₄] and ligand H-N₃L in equimolar ratio in methanol : ethanol (1 : 1). Two equivalent of ligand H-N₃L and monoequivalent of Fe(ClO₄)₂.xH₂O were utilized to synthesize bis complex of [Fe(H-N₃L)₂](ClO₄)₂, **2**. Similar procedure were followed to prepare Fe(Me-N₃L)Cl₃, **3** and [Fe(Me-N₃L)₂](ClO₄)₂, **4** using 1 : 1 equivalent of ligand Me-N₃L and Et₄N[FeCl₄] in complex **3** and two equivalent of ligand with one equivalent of Fe(ClO₄)₂.xH₂O was utilized for the synthesis of complex **4**. The schematic representation of synthetic procedures of complexes **1**, **2**, **3** and **4** has been summarized in Scheme 1. Synthesized complexes were characterized using various spectroscopic techniques.

During IR spectral studies the characteristic azomethine (ν_{-HC=N}) band for the free ligands were observed at ~1595 cm⁻¹. On metal complexation all the iron complexes exhibited shift in stretching frequency (Figs. S1-S4). These shifts exhibited the probable coordination of azomethine with the metal during complex formation¹⁸. Complex **2** and **4** also showed characteristic band near 1090 cm⁻¹ together with a band at 623 cm⁻¹ for non coordinated perchlorate ion¹⁹. Experimental IR data for all complexes have been deposited in Table 1.

Absorption spectral studies were also performed for all the complexes in methanol and depicted in Table 2 (Fig. S5). High energy band monitored below 250 nm is

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of synthesis of iron complexes.

Table 1. Data for IR and conductivity

Complex	IR data (cm^{-1}) ^a		Conductivity data ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) ^b
	$\nu_{\text{-HC=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{ClO}_4^-}$	
1	1606	–	52
2	1606	1091, 623	156
3	1595	–	41
4	1604	1095, 618	148

^aUsing KBr pellets, ^bSolvent : dimethylformamide.

Table 2. Electronic absorption spectral data

Complex	UV-Visible data ($\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$, $\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)
1	452 (500), 342.9 (7520), 300 (4930), 259 (7960), 221 (10740)
2	550 (210), 340 (31290), 294 (11010), 258 (14840), 238 (24160)
3	435 (790), 329 (3980), 260 (6500), 225 (8220)
4	552 (350), 345 (8720), 285 (9790), 250 (27740)

probably due to the intraligand $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions. The band originated at low energy in the range 400–550 nm could be due to $d-\pi^*$, chloro to iron and other LMCT transitions²⁰.

Conductivity measurements were performed at 25 °C in dimethylformamide at *ca.* 10^{-3}M . The values for the complexes **1** and **3** were found to be 52 and 41 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively which indicates the non-electrolytic behaviour of complexes in solution. On the other hand, molar conductivity of complexes **2** and **4** were having the values 156 and 148.0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively. These values suggested uni-bivalent (1 : 2) electrolytic behaviour of complexes in solution (Table 1)²¹. Effective magnetic moments for all the complexes were also calculated at 303 K. Values of magnetic moment for complex **1** and **3** was found to be 5.63 and 5.94 B.M. The values indicate high spin Fe^{III} metal centre in the complexes²². Complexes **2** and **4** have the value of magnetic moment 0.51 and 0.25 B.M. These values suggested low-spin Fe^{II} metal centre in the complexes^{8,23}. NMR spectra of metal complexes **2** and **4** also validate the presence of low spin Fe^{II} center. ESI-MS spectra of all the complexes were also recorded in acetonitrile solution at positive ion mode to confirm the synthesis of desired complexes. Complex **1** exhibited peak at m/z 414.1428 corresponding to the $[\text{M}-\text{Cl}]^+$. Similarly complex **2** showed the peak corresponding to m/z 731.1615 due to the $[\text{M}-\text{ClO}_4]^+$. Complex **3**

in acetonitrile under positive mode displayed the peaks at (m/z) 428.03, 325.14 and 301.14 and corresponding to $[\text{M}-\text{Cl}]^+$, $[\text{L}+\text{Na}]^+$ and $[\text{L}+\text{H}]^+$ at m/z : 428.02 (1.92%) $[\text{M}-\text{Cl}]^+$, 325.14 (25.24%) $[\text{L}+\text{Na}]^+$, 301.14 (65.10%) $[\text{L}+\text{H}]^+$ respectively. ESI-MS studies were also performed for complex **4** showed the peak corresponding to the m/z 759.1790 corresponding to the $[\text{M}-\text{ClO}_4]^+$ in acetonitrile (Figs. S6-S9). The presence of Fe^{II} low spin centre in the complexes **2** and **4** exhibited NMR spectra due to the diamagnetic nature. However coordination of the ligand with iron metal ion showed a change in chemical shift as compared to the free ligand. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectral data for both the complexes have been shown in Figs. S10-S13.

Theoretical studies :

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations have been found useful to determine the geometrical and structural properties of metal complexes²⁴. Herein we have performed DFT calculations to elucidate the structural property of complex **1**. Optimized structure of complex **1** has been depicted in Fig. 2 and characteristic structural parameters have been summarized in Table 3.

Fig. 2 Optimized geometry of the complex **1** using DFT.

Time dependent DFT (TD-DFT) calculations were also performed on the optimized structure of the complex to verify the electronic transitions in the UV-Visible spectrum with the theoretical one. All the theoretical calculations were performed in the gas phase. The HOMO and LUMO have been depicted in the Fig. 3.

Table 3 Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (deg) of complexes **1** obtained using DFT calculations

Bond distances		Bond angles	
DFT		DFT	
Fe(H-N ₃ L)Cl ₃			
Fe(1)-N(2)	2.186	Cl(3)-Fe1-N(2)	99.55
		N(2)-Fe1-Cl(1)	92.95
		N(2)-Fe1-Cl(2)	83.56
		N(2)-Fe1-N(3)	88.25
		N(2)-Fe1-N(4)	161.72
Fe(1)-N(3)	2.252	Cl(3)-Fe1-N(3)	171.83
		N(3)-Fe1-N(4)	74.87
Fe(1)-N(4)	2.145	Cl(3)-Fe1-N(4)	97.08
Fe(1)-Cl(1)	2.399	Cl(1)-Fe1-Cl(2)	166.37
		Cl(1)-Fe1-N(3)	85.06
		N(4)-Fe1-Cl(1)	92.53
		N(2)-Fe1-Cl(1)	92.95
Fe(1)-Cl(2)	2.454	N(4)-Fe1-Cl(2)	87.03
		Cl(2)-Fe1-N(3)	81.67
Fe(1)-Cl(3)	2.328	Cl(3)-Fe1-Cl(2)	96.71
		Cl(3)-Fe1-Cl(1)	96.87

Fig. 3. HOMO and LUMO of complex **1**.

TD-DFT calculations show contribution of molecular orbitals associated with the electronic transition (Table 4). Characteristic transitions have been depicted in Table 4 and both the theoretical and experimental values are in good agreement.

Electrochemical studies :

Redox properties of the metal complexes were investigated using electrochemical studies at a glassy carbon electrode using Ag/AgCl reference electrode. Fig. 4 shows cyclic voltammograms associated with the metal complexes **1** and **2** in acetonitrile solution. Both the complexes **1** and **2** showed a reversible peak at -0.85 and -0.97 V. Complexes also exhibited an irreversible peak at -0.35 and -0.78 V for complexes **1** and **2** respectively.

DNA binding studies :

Synthesized iron complexes were subjected to the DNA interaction studies using UV-Visible absorption, fluorescence and circular dichroism spectral studies. To investigate the DNA interaction studies of the complexes, stability of complexes were determined in the buffer solution. All the complexes were found to be stable in the buffer for more than 6 h. Figs. S14-S15 shows the stability of complexes in buffer. No shift was observed in the band, only a decrease in absorbance was observed. The small decrease in absorbance could be probably due to the gradual precipitation of the compounds with time. This indicated that the complexes retained their composition for the given period of time. Hence complexes could be utilized for further DNA interaction studies.

Absorption spectral studies have been utilized for the preliminary investigation of interactions of CT-DNA with the complexes. During experiments, small amount of DNA was added to a fixed complex concentration. Experiments were performed at physiological pH and changes in electronic properties were monitored. The UV-Visible data for all the complexes have been depicted in the Figs. 5–8.

Table 4. Calculated TD-DFT excitation energies (in eV), oscillator strengths (f) and nature of transitions in the complexes **1**

Composition (% Contribution)	E (eV)	Oscillator strength (f)	λ_{theo} (nm)	λ_{exp} (nm)
HOMO-3 \rightarrow LUMO+6 (29%)	4.1401	0.0511	299.47	300
HOMO-7 \rightarrow LUMO+4 (13%)				
HOMO-5 \rightarrow LUMO (74%)	3.6216	0.0077	342.9	342.35
HOMO-4 \rightarrow LUMO+5 (11%)				
HOMO-7 \rightarrow LUMO (23%)	2.7422	0.0002	452.13	452
HOMO-11 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (15%)				

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of 10^{-3} M solution of complexes (a) 1 and (b) 2 in acetonitrile.

Fig. 5. Absorption spectra of complex 1 in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) in the presence of increasing DNA concentration. (a) $[1] = 70 \mu\text{M}$, $[\text{DNA}] = 0\text{--}150 \mu\text{M}$. (b) plot of $[\text{DNA}]/\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ for the calculation of K_b of complex 1. Arrow indicates change in the absorbance with the increasing DNA concentration.

Fig. 6. Absorption spectra of complex 2 in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) in the presence of increasing DNA concentration. (a) $[2] = 100 \mu\text{M}$, $[\text{DNA}] = 0\text{--}250 \mu\text{M}$. (b) plot of $[\text{DNA}]/\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ for the calculation of K_b of complex 2. Arrow indicates change in the absorbance with the increasing DNA concentration.

During the interaction of CT-DNA with the complexes a change is observed in the intraligand transition at 340 nm. Hypochromism was observed in all the four com-

plexes 1-4 without any shift in wavelength. Binding constant (K_b) has been evaluated using Wolfe-Shimer equation²⁵ and have been tabulated in Table 5. The strength

Fig. 7. Absorption spectra of complex **3** in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) in the presence of increasing DNA concentration. (a) **[3]** = 70 μM , **[DNA]** = 0–200 μM , (b) plot of $[\text{DNA}]/\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f$ vs **[DNA]** for the calculation of K_b of complex **3**. Arrow indicates change in the absorbance with the increasing DNA concentration.

Fig. 8. Absorption spectra of complex **4** in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) in the presence of increasing DNA concentration. (a) **[4]** = 100 μM , **[DNA]** = 0–220 μM , (b) plot of $[\text{DNA}]/\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f$ vs **[DNA]** for the calculation of K_b of complex **4**. Arrow indicates change in the absorbance with the increasing DNA concentration.

Table 5. List of K_b for all the four complexes

Complex	K_b (M^{-1})
1	3.29×10^4 (Hypochromism)
2	5.01×10^4 (Hypochromism)
3	6.82×10^3 (Hypochromism)
4	3.35×10^3 (Hypochromism)

of binding is determined in terms of binding constant (K_b). The values of intrinsic binding constants (K_b) for complexes are in the range of 10^3 – 10^4 M^{-1} . These values are lower than the standard intercalator EB²⁶. These hypochromism along with the value of binding constant proposed binding of DNA probably through intercalation attributed to π - π^* stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore of ligands and DNA base pairs²⁷. The values for K_b are comparable to the reported values

for the iron complexes²⁸. Interaction of DNA with the complexes cannot be concluded only using UV-Visible absorption studies. Hence fluorescence and CD spectral studies must be performed to explain the accurate mode of interaction.

From the UV-Visible interaction studies it can be concluded that all the complexes were found to be interactive with the CT-DNA in given experimental condition.

Ethidium bromide (EB) displacement assay was performed using fluorescence spectral studies. EB is non-emissive but in presence of DNA it becomes fluorescent due to its strong intercalation with DNA base pairs²⁹. During studies displacement of EB with the complex is monitored. In order to optimize these properties a fixed amount of DNA is used with EB and titrated with a fixed amount of complexes at regular interval. Quenching in

fluorescence emission intensity was observed due to the displacement of EB from the CT-DNA (Figs. 9-12). The extent of quenching was calculated in terms of Stern-Volmer constant (K_{SV}) using linear Stern-Volmer equation.

Stern-Volmer plots clearly indicated that the fluores-

cence quenching of EB bound CT-DNA in the presence of complexes **1-4** and also in good linear agreement with the Stern-Volmer equation. These data suggested that the complexes bound with CT-DNA and values of Stern-Volmer constant (K_{SV}) have been summarized in the Table 6.

Fig. 9. (a) EB-DNA fluorescence quenching titration complex **1** (0–20 μM). (b) Stern-Volmer plots of F_0/F versus $[R]$ for complex shown. Tests were performed in the conditions of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) at 298 K; $[C_{\text{DNA}}] = 25 \mu\text{M}$, $[C_{\text{EtBr}}] = 0.5 \mu\text{M}$; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 250 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 585 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 10. (a) EB-DNA fluorescence quenching titration complex **2** (0–28 μM). (b) Stern-Volmer plots of F_0/F versus $[R]$ for complex shown. Tests were performed in the conditions of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) at 298 K; $[C_{\text{DNA}}] = 25 \mu\text{M}$, $[C_{\text{EtBr}}] = 0.5 \mu\text{M}$; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 250 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 585 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 11. (a) EB-DNA fluorescence quenching titration complex **3** (0–28 μM). (b) Stern-Volmer plots of F_0/F versus $[R]$ for complex shown. Tests were performed in the conditions of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) at 298 K; $[C_{\text{DNA}}] = 25 \mu\text{M}$, $[C_{\text{EtBr}}] = 0.5 \mu\text{M}$; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 250 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 585 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 12. (a) EB-DNA fluorescence quenching titration complex **4** (0–40 μM). (b) Stern-Volmer plots of F_0/F versus $[R]$ for complex shown. Tests were performed in the conditions of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) at 298 K; $C_{\text{DNA}} = 25 \mu\text{M}$, $C_{\text{EtBr}} = 0.5 \mu\text{M}$; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 250 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 598 \text{ nm}$.

Table 6. Data for Stern-Volmer quenching constant

Complex	$K_{\text{SV}} (\text{M}^{-1})$
1	9.2×10^4
2	4.0×10^4
3	3.2×10^4
4	2.7×10^4

The values of K_{SV} are found to be lesser than classical intercalator³⁰. Hence the partial displacement was observed in all the four complexes. The studies performed indicated probable mode of interaction with the CT-DNA is intercalation³¹.

During circular dichroism studies conformational changes in CT-DNA observed on interaction of metal complexes. DNA shows two bands in CD spectra, a positive band at 275 nm due to base stacking and a negative band at 245 nm due to helicity. The iron complexes were

not optically active and did not exhibit any CD spectra in the range 200–800 nm. On interaction with metal complexes CD spectra showed a decrease in the negative as well as in positive bands (Fig. 13) which represents significant interaction of CT-DNA with metal complexes. No shift in wavelength observed which indicates that these complexes do not affect the conformational changes of DNA³². These studies also suggested intercalative mode of interaction with the DNA³³.

Nuclease activity :

Nuclease activity of the representative complex **1** in presence of H_2O_2 was evaluated (Fig. 14). Cleavage of supercoiled *pBR322* DNA was observed with the complex **1** using gel electrophoresis. During the studies DMF content was kept below 10%. Variable concentration of complex **1** was employed to optimize the cleavage acti-

Fig. 13. Circular dichroism spectra in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) after 10 min incubation at 25 °C. (a) **1** (red) and **3** (blue), (b) **2** (red) and **4** (blue) with CT-DNA (black) and its interaction with complexes spectra recorded in 5% dimethylformamide.

vity. Fig. 14 depicts that intensity of the circular SC form decreases, while that of NC form increase (lane 4-7) without any activating agents. When an oxidising agent H₂O₂ was added to the DNA the NC form further increased (lane 8).

Fig. 14. Gel electrophoresis separations showing the cleavage of supercoiled *pBR322* DNA (100 ng) by variable concentration of complexes **1** in 10% DMF incubated at 37 °C for 2 h. Lane 1 : DNA, lane 2 : DNA + FeCl₃ (100 μM), lane 3 : DNA + H-N₃L, lane 4 : DNA + **1** (10 μM), lane 5 : DNA + **1** (25 μM), lane 6 : DNA + **1** (50 μM), lane 7 : DNA + **1** (100 μM), lane 8 : DNA + **1** (100 μM) + H₂O₂ (100 μM), lane 9 : DNA + H₂O₂ (100 μM), lane 10 : DNA + DMF (2 μL).

Quantitative representation of cleavage has been depicted in the Fig. 15. From the activity it is clear that with the increased amount of complex concentration the DNA is cleaved and a mixture of nicked DNA and supercoiled DNA obtained in presence of H₂O₂.

Fig. 15. Bar diagram representation of SC and NC form during nuclease activity of complex **1**.

Conclusions

A new family of mononuclear iron complexes have been synthesized and characterized using various spectroscopic techniques. ESI-MS and NMR spectral studies clearly indicated the formation of complexes. DFT and TD-DFT calculations were performed on complex **1** to optimize geometrical and structural parameters. Redox properties of complexes were examined by electrochemical studies and the results indicated ligand centred redox

activity. For advancement of medicinal inorganic chemistry a better understanding of mechanism of metal complexes interaction with the DNA is needed. Hence DNA interaction studies were performed utilizing these complexes. DNA binding studies were optimized using UV-Visible, fluorescence and circular dichroism spectral studies. These studies indicated interaction is probably due to the intercalation mode of binding. Complex **1** was also subjected to the nuclease activity. Complex **1** was effective artificial chemical nuclease in presence of H₂O₂ under physiological pH. Determination of molecular structure by X-ray crystallography and other reactivity studies of these complexes are under progress.

Supplementary information

All additional information related to the characterization of the complexes such as IR, UV-Visible, ESI-MS, NMR spectral studies have been deposited in the supporting information file.

Acknowledgement

KG is thankful to DST-SERB, India for financial assistance no. SR/S1/IC-47/2012 dated 21-OCT-2013. SR is thankful to UGC, India, for financial assistance. AM and OS are thankful to MHRD, India for financial support.

References

- (a) M. Velusamy, R. Mayilmurugan and M. Palaniandavar, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2005, **99**, 1032; (b) K. Visvagesan, R. Mayilmurugan, E. Suresh and M. Palaniandavar, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 10294.
- B. Kripli, G. Baráth, É. Balogh-Hergovich, M. Giorgi, A. J. Simaan, L. Párkányi, J. S. Pap, J. Kaizer and G. Speier, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **14**, 205.
- T. Kojima, R. A. Leising, S. Yan and L. Que (Jr.), *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 11328.
- Y. Hitomi, K. Arakawa, T. Funabiki and M. Kodera, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2012, **51**, 3448.
- G. Roelfes, M. Lubben, R. Hage, L. Que, (Jr.) and B. L. Feringa, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2000, **6**, 2152.
- (a) M. A. Hoselton, L. J. Wilson and R. S. Drago, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 1722; (b) M. Seredyuk, A. B. Gaspar, V. Ksenofontov, Y. Galyametdinov, J. Kusz and P. Gütllich, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2008, **18**, 2089; (c) A. C. Bowman, C. Milsman, E. Bill, Z. R. Turner, E. Lobkovsky, S. DeBeer, K. Wieghardt and P. J. Chirik, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 17353.
- R. K. O'Reilly, V. C. Gibson, A. J. P. White and D. J. Williams, *Polyhedron*, 2004, **23**, 2921.

8. K. Ghosh, N. Tyagi, A. K. Dhara and U. P. Singh, *Chem. Asian J.*, 2014, **10**, 350.
9. (a) J. M. Hoyt, V. A. Schmidt, A. M. Tondreau and P. J. Chirik, *Science*, 2015, **349**, 960; (b) V. A. Schmidt, J. M. Hoyt, G. M. Margulieux and P. J. Chirik, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2015, **137**, 7903; (c) G. W. Margulieux, Z. R. Turner and P. J. Chirik, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2014, **53**, 14211; (d) J. M. Darmon, R. P. Yu, S. P. Semproni, Z. R. Turner, S. C. E. Stieber, S. DeBeer and P. J. Chirik, *Organometallics*, 2014, **33**, 5423; (e) C. C. H. Atienza, T. Diao, K. J. Weller, S. A. Nye, K. M. Lewis, J. G. P. Delis, J. L. Boyer, A. K. Roy and P. J. Chirik, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **136**, 12108; (f) C. Milsman, S. P. Semproni and P. J. Chirik, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **136**, 12099.
10. (a) K. Ghosh, P. Kumar, V. Mohan and U. P. Singh, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **15**, 56; (b) K. Ghosh, P. Kumar, N. Tyagi and U. P. Singh, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **49**, 7614; (c) K. Ghosh, P. Kumar, V. Mohan, U. P. Singh, S. Kasiri and S. S. Mandal, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 3343; (d) K. Ghosh, P. Kumar, N. Tyagi, U. P. Singh, V. Aggarwal and M. C. Baratto, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 3770; (e) K. Ghosh, N. Tyagi, P. Kumar, U. P. Singh and N. Goel, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2010, **104**, 9; (f) K. Ghosh, N. Tyagi and P. Kumar, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **13**, 380; (g) K. Ghosh, P. Kumar, N. Tyagi, U. P. Singh, N. Goel, A. Chakraborty, P. Roy and M. C. Baratto, *Polyhedron*, 2011, **30**, 2667; (h) K. Ghosh, P. Kumar, N. Tyagi, U. P. Singh and N. Goel, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **14**, 489; (i) K. Ghosh, P. Kumar and N. Tyagi, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 2011, **375**, 77; (j) K. Ghosh, N. Tyagi, P. Kumar, S. Rathi and U. P. Singh, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **20**, 167; (k) K. Ghosh, V. Mohan, P. Kumar and U. P. Singh, *Polyhedron*, 2013, **49**, 167; (l) K. Ghosh, N. Tyagi, P. Kumar and U. P. Singh, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2014, **412**, 20; (m) K. Ghosh, N. Tyagi, H. Kumar and S. Rathi, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2015, **146**, 292; (n) N. Tyagi, A. Chakraborty, U. P. Singh, P. Roy and K. Ghosh, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2015, **13**, 11445.
11. K. Ghosh, S. Rathi and A. Maji (Submitted).
12. (a) P. De, S. Maji, A. D. Chowdhury, S. M. Mobin, T. K. Mondal, A. Paretzki and G. K. Lahiri, *Dalton Trans.*, 2011, **40**, 12527; (b) K. Karidi, A. Garoufis, A. Tsipis, N. Hadjiliadis, H. Den Dulk and J. Reedijk, *Dalton Trans.*, 2005, 1176.
13. J. Marmur, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1961, **3**, 208.
14. M. E. Reichmann, S. A. Rice, C. A. Thomas and P. Doty, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 3047.
15. A. Dimitrakopoulou, C. Dendrinou-Samara, A. A. Pantazaki, M. Alexiou, E. Nordlander and D. P. Kessissoglou, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2008, **102**, 618.
16. Y. Shao, X. Sheng, Y. Li, Z. L. Jia, J. J. Zhang, F. Liu and G. Y. Lu, *Bioconjugate Chem.*, 2008, **19**, 1840.
17. (a) C. Hiort, B. Norden and A. Rodger, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 1971; (b) A. Rodger, B. Norden, P. Rodger and P. J. Bates, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2002, **1**, 49; (c) T. Hard and B. Norden, *Biopolymers*, 1986, **25**, 1209.
18. A. K. Patra, M. M. Olmstead and P. K. Mascharak, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2002, **41**, 5403.
19. M. R. Rosenthal, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1973, **50**, 331.
20. K. Nakamoto, in "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, 1978; (b) A. Sreekanth and M. R. P. Kurup, *Polyhedron*, 2004, **23**, 969; (c) T. Sarkar, S. Banerjee and A. Hussain, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 29276.
21. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
22. D. T. Mark, N. H. David and S. Ekkehard, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 3941.
23. S. A. Cotton, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **8**, 185.
24. (a) J. C. Cramer, in "Essentials of Computational Chemistry, Theories and Models", John Wiley & Sons, 2004; (b) W. Koch and M. C. Holthausen, "A Chemist's Guide to Density Functional Theory", Wiley-VCH, New York, 2001; (c) A. J. Cohen, P. Mori-Sánchez and W. Yang, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 289; (d) A. D. McLean and G. S. Chandler, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2012, **72**, 5639; (e) K. Raghavachari, J. S. Binkley, R. Seeger and J. A. Pople, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1980, **72**, 650.
25. A. Wolfe, G. Shimer and T. Meehan, *Biochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 6392.
26. J. B. Le Pecq and C. Paoletti, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 196, **727**, 87.
27. (a) P. J. Cox, G. Psomas and C. A. Bolos, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **17**, 6054; (b) T. M. Kelly, A. B. Tossi, D. J. McConnell and T. C. Streckas, *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 1985, **13**, 6017; (c) A. M. Pyle, J. P. Rehmann, R. Meshoyrer, C. V. Kumar, N. J. Turro and J. K. Barton, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 3053.
28. J. Qian, J.-L. Tian, L. Feng, W. Gu, X.-J. Zhao and S.-P. Yan, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 1260.
29. N. Husain, R. A. Agbaria and I. M. Warner, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 10857.
30. J.-B. Lepecq and C. Paoletti, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1967, **27**, 87.
31. (a) N. Shahabadi, Z. M. Kalar and N. H. Moghadam, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2012, **96**, 723; (b) C. W. Jiang, H. Chao, H. Li and L. N. Ji, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2003, **93**, 247.
32. J. Liu, H. Zhang, C. Chen, H. Deng, T. Lu and L. Ji, *Dalton Trans.*, 2003, 114.
33. (a) R. Indumathy, T. Weyhermuller and B. Unni Nair, *Dalton Trans.*, 2010, **39**, 2087; (b) G. Zhang, X. Hu and P. Fu, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (B)*, 2012, **108**, 53; (c) F. Arjmand, G. C. Sharma, M. Muddassir and S. Tabassum, *Chirality*, 2011, **23**, 557; (d) M. T. Behnamfar, H. Hadadzadeh, J. Simpson, F. Darabi, A. Shahpiri, T. Khayamian, M. Ebrahimi, H. A. Rudbari and M. Salimi, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2015, **134**, 502.